

Wheelchair Accessibility to Public Buildings in Songea Municipality

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Abstract:

Wheelchair accessibility to public buildings is an increasing area of important in research in the field of rehabilitation medicine worldwide, but wheelchair accessibility to public buildings in developing countries is a poorly researched phenomena making the situation unclear. The study assessed wheelchair accessibility of public buildings in Songea Municipality. A descriptive cross sectional survey where by objective assessment of 16 public buildings was performed in Songea Municipality using a standard survey guideline (Americans with Disabilities Act Guideline). Cluster sampling

technique was used to sample the available buildings into different clusters and 19 buildings were sampled randomly from each cluster. The overall score of accessibility compliance was 38%. Of the five areas of accessibility assessed, entrance had the highest compliance of 92%, and parking had lowest score of 0%, others were accessible route 31%, ramp 20% and toilet 17%. The buildings which were built before a year 2010 had a mean score of 20.5% and those built after the year 2010 had a mean score of 55.2%. The results of the current study shows that most of public buildings surveyed in Songea Municipal are inaccessible to wheelchair users despite the presence of building regulations and persons with disability act of 2010. The study recommends the enforcement of the law by the government to all public buildings, emphasis to be made on parking, ramps, toilets and accessible routes. The study also recommends remodeling of the available inaccessible elements by the buildings administrators.

Keywords: *Wheelchair Accessibility, Public Buildings, Songea Municipal.*

Introduction

Disability is the loss or limitation of opportunities to take part in the normal life of the community on an equal level with others due to physical, mental or social factors (NBS,2018) The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) argued that disability is an umbrella term, covering impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions. Thus disability is a complex phenomenon,

reflecting an interaction between features of a person's body and features of the society in which he or she lives (WHO, 2020). One of the major roles of rehabilitation is to make a person with disability reach fullest physical potential consistent with the environmental limitations. A wheelchair is the device most commonly used to provide mobility to those persons and thus giving chance to participate in social, cultural, functional and even the environment itself.

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Wheelchair users require mobility buildings, offering access, adequate space in all rooms, doorways and passages for wheelchair circulation and handles, switches, windows and work surfaces at wheelchair height (Hamzat *et al.*, 2015). In developed countries like United States of America and Europe, there is compliance to building accessibility guideline acts and policies to people with disabilities especially the wheelchairs users which underpins their building permit but not to hundred percent compliance. The new buildings which are built comply with the national building regulations. Also in Malaysia, two buildings out of five score 80% compliant to the design requirements from Malaysian Standards and universal design guidelines. In the same study one building recorded highest score of 81.33% among the five buildings (Kadir *et al.*, 2019). In Africa, few countries have conducted studies on wheelchair accessibility to public buildings and the results showed wheelchair accessibility was less than fifty percent. In Ibadan Nigeria only 20% of public buildings have facilities that provide basic services for health, recreation, social, financial, employment, and education needs which were accessible to wheelchair users. (Hamzat *et al.*, 2015) Apart from Nigeria, In Accra Ghana revealed that the three buildings which were assessed are partly compliant with the guidelines in the international building instruments, but not totally disability -friendly. Secondly, parts of all the facilities, such as the car parks, main entrances, ramps, staircases and corridors, were not readily accessible to PWDs. Also, fittings, such as directional signs, underfoot warnings, Braille texts, seats for wheelchair users were absent in most of the buildings (Anon, 2019).

Around one in every ten wheelchair users in Tanzania reported that they could not access work, schools, shops, banks and post office. About 2 in every 10 wheelchair users reported their place of worship to be inaccessible. This suggests that places outside the home were inaccessible for wheelchair users. In addition, a number of people reported that they 'never go' to places outside of their homes. The reasons for this need further investigation. This could be because of the places being inaccessible or

because of not wanting to go there (NBS,2018). Another study in Tanzania conducted by Majinge 2013 in five academic university libraries found out that the wheelchair users in those buildings were not inclusive (Majinge,2013). The role of rehabilitation to wheelchair users is to make them reach the fullest physical potential consistent with their environment. However this cannot be achieved, if the public buildings are not friendly to wheelchair users .According to People with Disability Act 2010 in Tanzania, each public building is required to be accessible to all people with disabilities by complying with accessibility regulations. Few studies available have been conducted only for general population of disabled persons and not specifically for wheelchair users making the situation unclear. So this study aims at assessing the wheelchair accessibility to public buildings in Songea municipality. Therefore the present aimed at assessing the accessibility of public buildings for wheelchair users in Songea municipality one of the five Districts of Ruvuma Region in Tanzania.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature

Wheelchair

Wheelchair is a device providing wheeled mobility and seating support for a person with difficulty in walking or moving around.

Accessibility

Accessibility is defined as the freedom or ability of people to reach their basic needs so as to increase their quality of life

Public Building

Public building is any building that is used to provide services to the people.

Theoretical Framework

Poststructural Critical Theory

Siegle, (1997) a proponent of the Poststructural critical theory postulates that though significant improvements in addressing integrated accessibility to the built environment have been

brought about through the use of Universal Design, its implementation has been unsuccessful in dealing with many of the underlying social issues. He therefore argues that the Poststructural critical theory challenges underlying belief systems as a channel for assessing the principles of Universal Design simultaneously with the social and cultural beliefs upon which concerns on accessibility especially the physically handicapped rests (Siegle, 1997).

Further, Siegle (1997) contends that the Poststructural critical theory also challenges continuing problems of frequent segregation of the able and disabled populations, where in lieu of providing an integrated accessible building infrastructure; accessible accommodations exist in building infrastructure amongst a predominantly inaccessible whole. Such segregation exists as a significant social problem based not on malice, but rather entrenched concepts of disability held by our society (Siegle, 1997). Orens, (1997) another proponent of the Poststructural critical theory argues that the theory exposes and provides a critique to these conceptual beliefs, has the ability to address the underlying issues and in the process placing Universal Design within a broader social and cultural context.

In adopting this theory this study therefore contends that while accessibility is generally conceived as a problem of physical barriers, social and psychological barriers performs a crucial role in the separation of society into able and disabled populations (Orens, 1997). In providing a platform to advance the principles of Universal Design (U.D) such as; equitable use, low physical effort, simple and intuitive use and flexibility in use, the theory helps to addresses research questions; 1 on the effect of the built environment, 3 on financial resources by challenging social and cultural beliefs it calls for better disability provisions for accessibility funding and 4 on the effect of public awareness by exposing and critiquing existing social beliefs on the disabled.

Empirical Literature

Welage et al, (2011) from university of Colombo did a literature review on wheelchair accessibility to public buildings and reported that; from the nine studies examined parking facilities, he found the least degree of compliance with wheelchair accessibility requirements (with regard to the number of parking slots for wheelchair users, the location and the display of the international symbol of access). The percentage of compliance was better in the US (71–95%, and Turkey 53% than in Zimbabwe (19%) and the United Arab Emirates (18%).

In Istanbul turkey a descriptive study done by Evcil, (2018) reported that, all 25 buildings surveyed, accessible route had a mean compliance of 69% although had narrow sidewalk, prolapsed paving stones and some obstacles like advertisement boards and pots of flowers in another descriptive study done by Fischer 2004 in UAE among 17 buildings assessed, accessible routes had highest compliant with mean of 79%.

While in Nigeria a descriptive study of Lawal (2013) showed that Seventeen out of twenty libraries; representing (85%) are with narrow doors not suitable for easy accessibility of wheelchair while only three libraries, representing (15%) have wide doors that are wheelchair accessible. In Canada a study done by Bennet (2018) reported that all 79 buildings assessed had ramps, only 2.6% of the ramps evaluated met the standards of the wheelchair ramp and in another descriptive study done by Lily (2013) in Botswana reported that Eight out of the 19 assessed buildings had ramps, but only two of them had handrails on the ramps and some of the ramps slope specification was not met, no handrails and one of them landed straight into the public road.(Bennett et al. 2009)

A cross sectional study done by Maftalane (2013) in Botswana found that toilets were available at different floor levels. Eight out of nineteen buildings had toilets that meant for wheelchair users. But, only four of those had space to transfer from the wheelchair to the toilet. Seven buildings had washbasins with knee space and taps reachable from a seated position. The toilets

had grab bars but some items and accessories such as light switches, mirrors, toilet paper holders, soap dispensers, and hand dryers were too high. In Ghana a study of Anon (2019) showed that two buildings out of three had satisfactory restrooms for wheelchair users. The restrooms had very low-level water closets, vertical and horizontal grab rails and hand washbasins close to them. The rooms had ample space for maneuvering by wheelchairs.

Material and Methods

This study employed descriptive cross-sectional study design while the study was conducted at Songea municipality which is located at Ruvuma region; the region has total population of 1,376,891 people and covers an area of 64,493 square kilometers of the entire area of Tanzania mainland. Songea municipal is the Regional Headquarter. It is the major centre for administrative and commercial activities in the Region.

Furthermore the study population included selected buildings in Songea municipality. A building was considered as a public building if it was meant for public use, or could be used by any member of the community. Among buildings taken for this study were government agencies, commercial buildings, administrative buildings, educational facilities and Worship buildings. Only buildings solely housing one public service were included. Within this cross-section, 77 buildings were identified using the municipal database as a source.

Meanwhile cluster and simple random sampling technique were used to select the public buildings. Of the 77 buildings, 19 clusters were obtained and 19 buildings were randomly chosen to be surveyed. These 19 buildings included a regional hospital, regional court, three commercial buildings, two banks, a hotel, Teaching College, four administrative buildings, Central market, two primary and three secondary schools.

The instrument used was a checklist form covering five accessibility areas: parking, ramps, entrances, accessible routes, toilets. For each

area there are different standards or items described. The survey comprised 37 items which were adopted by the investigator directly from the Americans with Disabilities Act Guidelines (ADAAG) and its Checklist for Buildings and Facilities. A direct observational method was used to collect data. A check list adopted from American with Disability Act Accessibility Guideline (ADAAG) was used to ensure that all items needed to assess the accessibility of the selected item are observed, measured and recorded. One individual previously coached in the use of the survey form and measurements assisted the researcher on the procedure. The same measuring tape was used to determine the dimensions of the items.

The researcher coded the collected data and entered in Microsoft Excel 2007. A descriptive analysis of percentages was done using the Statistical Package for the Social Scientists (SPSS) version 23. To check the level of compliance to the guidelines of the instrument descriptive statistics of simple percentages and means were used. Each building was scored as compliant or non-compliant with each of the relevant checklist items within the accessibility areas. The results reflect the percentage of items in compliance for each building in each area and the percentage of buildings in compliance for each item in each area. Also the results show the average percentage of compliance of all the relevant areas for each building and the average percentage of compliance of each area for all the buildings. Percentages were calculated on the basis of only those items and areas that applied and results were presented in terms of tables.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Faculty of Rehabilitation Medicine at Kilimanjaro Christian Medical University College and Course Coordinator. Permission to survey the buildings within the municipal was obtained from the Regional Administrative Secretary, District Administrative Secretary and director of the municipal through a written letter. The buildings' managers were approached and presented with a letter describing the study, the confidential nature of the data to be recorded, the voluntary participation to the study was requested and the care that would be taken not

to obstruct the activity of the site in question while measurements were performed. After signed approval from the building’s manager was received, data was collected in the accessibility areas mentioned using the survey form through direct observations and measurements.

Findings and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study. Demographic characteristics of the buildings, the standards of parking, accessible route, ramp, entrance and toilet are all presented. Of the 19 public buildings approached 16 consented to participate and were evaluated. Two sites declined and one site did not reply even after

several approaches. The percentage of compliance of each accessibility area was calculated by taking the available standards over the required standards by the guideline.

Demographic Characteristics of the Buildings

About 16 buildings surveyed, four were Schools, one bank, a hotel, four administrative buildings, a teaching college, three commercial buildings, church and central market. Six buildings were built between 1950 and 2000; 5 buildings were built between 2000 and 2010 and 4 buildings were built between 2010 and 2015 and one had unknown year of construction. The number of floors of the buildings ranged from zero to four floors.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Buildings

NO.	Function of the buildings	Number of floors	Year of construction
1	school 1	0	1957
2	Church	0	1968
3	Hotel	0	2003
4	Administrative 1	3	1998
5	school 2	1	2004
6	Bank	0	2015
7	school 3	0	2007
8	Administrative 2	1	Unknown
9	Administrative 3	2	2012
10	Administrative 4	2	2013
11	College	2	1968
12	Commercial 1	3	2010
13	Commercial 2	4	2015
14	Commercial 3	3	2000
15	Central market	0	2004
16	School 4	0	1950

Source: Field Data, 2024

Overall Compliance of Five Accessibility Areas at 16 Public Buildings

The overall average score of compliance was 38% which was calculated as total average score of each accessibility area of sixteen public buildings. Of the 16 buildings 3(19%) complied

with the guideline. One out of three buildings had highest compliance of 80%, out of five areas assessed, parking had lowest compliance of (0%) followed by toilets (17%), Ramp (20%),and Route (31%).Only entrance had highest compliance of 92%.

Table 2. Percentage Compliance of Five Accessibility Areas at 16 Public Buildings in Songea Municipality

Building(constructed)	Areas (%)					Average
	Parking	Route	Ramp	Entrance	Toilet	
School 1(1957)	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	20%
Church (1968)	0%	0%	0%	75%	0%	10%
Hotel (2003)	0%	83%	0%	75%	25%	32%
Administrative office 1(1998)	0%	83%	0%	100%	13%	39%
School 2(2004)	0%	50%	0%	100%	13%	33%
Bank (2015)	0%	100%	100%	100%	25%	65%
School 3(2007)	0%	0%	57%	100%	13%	34%
Administrative office 2	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	20%
Administrative offices 4 (2012)	0%	83%	71%	100%	13%	53%
Administrative office 3(2013)	0%	100%	100%	100%	100%	80%
College 1(1968)	0%	0%	0%	75%	0%	10%
Commercial building 1(2010)	0%	0%	0%	100%	13%	23%
Commercial building 2(2015)	0%	0%	0%	100%	25%	25%
Commercial building 3(2000)	0%	0%	0%	100%	25%	25%
Central market (2004)	0%	0%	0%	75%	13%	13%
School4 (1950)	0%	0%	0%	75%	0%	10%
Average	0%	31%	20%	92%	17%	38%

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

f)

g)

h)

Figure 1 (a-h). Some of the Public Buildings in Songea Municipality

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

f)

g)

h)

Figure 2(a-h). Some of the Accessibility Areas of the Buildings (Ramp, Stairs without Ramps, Parking, Route without Curbramp, Pit Toilet, Toilet Door)

The results of the present study shows that the average percentage score of compliance of the 16 buildings was 38%, this is almost similar to the study done in Nigeria by Hamzat, (2015), of which compliance was around 20%, and a study done in Istanbul (2019) by Evcil which reported the overall compliance to be 29%. This could be attributed to poor adherence to international policy concerning wheelchair accessibility to public buildings. For Tanzania in particular the enforcement of the people with disability act took place in the year 2010. In the present study most of the buildings were built below the year 2010, only three buildings were built after year 2010. This could explain why there was poor compliance in Songea region. But the results of the current study are contrary to the study done in Al Ain (UAE) 2014 by Fischer on seventeen public buildings which reported that the overall compliance score was 52%. According to the author much were actually been accomplished in the field of wheelchair accessibility of public buildings in the UAE city of Al Ain, despite the absence of legislation. Environmental and economic differences between the two countries could explain the difference.

The findings of this study indicate that the public buildings included in the present study differed markedly in terms of the accessibility provided for wheelchair users, from the lowest compliance score of the school, church and college with 10%, to the highest score of the administrative offices with 80%. Similar differences between the highest and lowest scores have been previously reported by Fischer, 2004.

Parking, accessible route, ramps and toilets were the accessibility areas with the least compliance scores. This is almost similar to the previously study reported by (Fischer, 2004; Maftalane, 2015; Estes et al., 2004; LaBan and Grimm, 2010). But is contrary to the study done by Welage, 2011; Anon, (2019) again this may be due economic level and awareness level difference between the two countries. Entrance was the area of accessibility for wheelchair users with the highest compliance score, again lie in

line with previous studies by Fidzani 2013; Hamzat 2005; Lawal, 2013. The buildings had a clear opening width of at least 81.5 cm and complied with the entrances' threshold standards, doors in all of the entrances had accessible handles height ≤ 120 cm.

In this study, the current buildings which were built between 2010 and 2015 were little bit compliant with wheelchair accessibility Act with a mean score of 55.2%. As mentioned previously this could be explained by the enforcement of PWD act of 2010 in Tanzania. The Act requires every public building which provides services to the public to be accessible to all persons with disabilities by complying with accessibility regulations. The buildings which were built below the year 2010 had an average compliance of 20.5%, which could be due to the fact that most of these buildings were built before the law was enforced.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The results of the current study show that most of public buildings assessed in Songea Municipal are inaccessible to wheelchair users despite the presence of building regulations and persons with disability act of 2010. The buildings which were built in the year before 2010 had low accessibility percentage compliance compared to those buildings built after 2010. Because of the small sample and area of coverage, the findings of the present study may not be generalized. Further extensive research directed to buildings accessibility to wheelchair users with wide coverage can provide important information regarding the magnitude of the problem in Tanzania. Furthermore research should be conducted on awareness of civil engineers and architects to the right of persons with disability to access public buildings.

The current study shows that an effort is needed by the government to enforce the building regulations through the regional engineers especially for the newly built public buildings so as to facilitate wheelchair accessibility, since some of the elements of wheelchair accessibility

guideline were present in some approached newly public buildings but others were not or were present with sub-standards. Since the purpose of public buildings is to provide public services to all people in the society, public buildings administrators of old buildings should consider the remodeling of some elements in the of the buildings so that wheelchair users have access to them. Remodeling could be easier than building or installing a new item. Sensitization of the society on the need of the accessibility to public building for wheelchair users through awareness programs via seminars, workshops and public education through media.

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